

Age-Related Modulation of Decision-Making Strategies And Functional Connectivity

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Abstract

Decision-making involves coordinated activity across distributed neural circuits, including the motor cortex, basal ganglia, and prefrontal cortex. The secondary motor cortex (M2/MOs) flexibly encodes multiple decision strategies, enabling adaptive behavior. Aging disrupts neural coordination and may impair this flexibility. Using Neuropixels data from mice performing a visual discrimination task, we analyzed functional connectivity between MOs, prefrontal cortex and basal ganglia across age groups. Young mice showed stronger MOs connectivity indicating robust network engagement. Older mice exhibited reduced linear correlation strength, though nonlinear mutual information remained relatively preserved. Behaviorally, logistic regression and contrast sensitivity analyses revealed mice reach peak performance in early adulthood, while younger and older mice displayed weaker sensory-driven strategies. These results suggest that aging selectively impairs neural synchrony and flexibility in strategy use, highlighting MOs–PFC–BG network as key substrates for adaptive decision-making across the lifespan.

1. Description

Decision-making involves integrating sensory information, internal states, and flexible strategies through a distributed network including the motor cortex, basal ganglia, and prefrontal cortex. The secondary motor cortex (M2/MOs) is key for initiating actions and supporting diverse decision strategies, while the prefrontal cortex (PFC) contributes to inference-based choices. Recent findings (Cazettes et al., 2023) show that M2 not only encodes current decision variables but also retains latent representations for alternative strategies, enabling flexible, adaptive behavior. Traditional models view decision-making as following a single, stable strategy, but recent evidence (Ashwood et al., 2022) reveals that behavior often reflects multiple interleaved strategies, with abrupt switches between stable neural states. These include an "engaged" state driven by sensory evidence and "disengaged" states marked by biases and reduced sensory reliance. An intriguing feature of sensory decision-making is the occurrence of "lapses," where an individual makes an incorrect choice even when the sensory evidence is clear and strong suggesting temporary disruptions in attention or memory rather than sensory processing failures. Aging affects decision-making by altering brain connectivity and neural function, leading to cognitive decline marked by slower processing, reduced attention, and impaired spatial learning and motor skills. These changes are linked to neural circuit disruptions such as cortical hyperexcitability, impaired synaptic plasticity, and imbalances in excitation and inhibition (Radulescu et al., 2021). Since brain regions involved in managing bias and behavioral strategy transitions are especially vulnerable to age-related changes (Mohammadi et al., 2025), aging may specifically alter the neural mechanisms that distinguish engaged from disengaged decision-making states.

Building on evidence that M2 supports both active encoding and flexible switching of decision variables, we will perform correlation analyses between M2 and selected regions of the basal ganglia and PFC to assess functional connectivity during task performance. We will compare these connectivity patterns across age groups to examine how aging alters the neural coordination underlying decision-making. Additionally, we will analyze behavioral data to identify when mice are using engaged versus disengaged decision-making strategies across sessions. This will allow us to examine how strategy use varies with age.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Dataset Description

This study uses data from (Steinmetz et al., 2019) involving 39 sessions across 10 mice performing a visual discrimination task. Neural activity was recorded using Neuropixels probes while mice turned a wheel to indicate the side with higher contrast. The dataset includes detailed behavioral measures—such as wheel movements, pupil size, facial motion, and licking—as well as precise timing of task events. This allows for a comprehensive analysis of how neural activity relates to behavior and task engagement.

2.2. Neural Analysis

We performed functional connectivity analyses focusing on regions implicated in decision-making and sensory-motor integration

2.2.1. Neural Data for Correlation Analysis

To examine functional connectivity between MOs and key regions of PFC and Basal Ganglia (BG), we conducted trial-wise Pearson correlation analyses using Local Field Potential (LFP)

recordings. We selected regions known for their roles in adaptive decision-making: within the PFC—the Anterior Cingulate Area (ACA), Infralimbic Area (ILA), Prelimbic Area (PL), and Orbital Area (ORB)—and within the BG—the Nucleus Accumbens (ACB) and Lateral Septal Nucleus (LS)—. Only sessions with simultaneous recordings from MOs and at least one region of interest (ROI) were analyzed. For each trial, we calculated Pearson correlations between MOs and each ROI's LFP signals, then averaged these trial-level correlations to obtain session-level connectivity matrices. These were further averaged across sessions to derive mean correlation values for each MOs–PFC and MOs–BG pair.

2.2.2. Age-Related Differences in Functional Connectivity

We examined age-related differences in functional connectivity among three key brain regions—primary visual area (VISp), ACA, and MOs—chosen for their roles in sensory processing, attention/decision-making, and motor planning. Only sessions with LFP recordings from all three regions were included. To explore developmental and aging effects, we selected mice from three distinct age groups: young adult (11 weeks), mature adult (20 weeks), and late adult (46 weeks). Functional connectivity was quantified using both Pearson correlation (linear) and mutual information (nonlinear) to assess interactions across age groups.

2.3. Behavioral Analysis

To investigate the effects of aging on decision-making behavior, we analyzed behavioral data from three mice—Cori (11 weeks), Radnitz (20 weeks), and Moniz (30 weeks)—selected based on their age distribution, which spans early to mid-adulthood, and because each had at least three recorded behavioral sessions, allowing us to assess changes and consistency in behavior across sessions. We aimed to assess whether their choices were driven by sensory evidence (engaged

strategy) or internal biases (less engaged strategy). Two complementary methods were used to quantify and track these strategies across sessions and age groups.

2.3.1. Psychometric Function via Logistic Regression

We modeled the probability of choosing the right side as a function of contrast difference using logistic regression. The task involved a binary decision, where on each trial the mouse chose either the left or right side based on visual contrast cues. To ensure meaningful analysis, only valid trials—those with non-zero responses—were included, thereby excluding unclear decisions. The logistic model was defined as:

$$P(\textit{choose right}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta\textit{contrast}))}$$

In this model, the slope (β_1) indicates sensitivity to contrast differences, with higher values reflecting more sensory-driven (engaged) decisions, while the intercept (β_0) captures side bias. Model fit was evaluated using pseudo- R^2 to measure how well contrast predicted behavior across sessions.

2.3.2. Psychometric Behavior via Contrast Sensitivity

The second method focused on the relationship between performance accuracy and task difficulty, defined by the absolute contrast difference between left and right stimuli. For each session, we computed the mouse's accuracy at each unique contrast level. We then assessed whether accuracy increased with greater contrast differences—a sign of an engaged strategy that reflects sensitivity to sensory evidence. To quantify this relationship, we used Spearman's rank correlation defined as :

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2-1)}$$

Where d is the difference between the ranks of contrast level and accuracy for the i -th data point, n is the number of unique contrast levels in the session.

3.Results

3.1.Functional Connectivity of MOs with PFC and BG

MOs showed strong positive correlations with both PFC and BG indicates a strong functional coupling between MOs and these regions during task engagement. The highest correlation within the PFC was with ACA (~0.86), and the lowest with ILA (~0.72). In the BG, MOs correlated strongly with ACB (~0.77) and LS (~0.79). These findings highlight MOs' tight coupling with brain regions critical for adaptive behavior, as summarized in Figure 1A.

3.2.Age-Dependent Decline in Functional Connectivity

Functional connectivity strength between MOs, ACA, and VISp was assessed using the mean off-diagonal Pearson correlation coefficient (capturing linear dependencies) and the mean off-diagonal mutual information (MI) (capturing nonlinear dependencies). The youngest mouse (11 weeks) showed the strongest connectivity, while the oldest (46 weeks) had the weakest linear correlations. Nonlinear connectivity (MI) declined from 11 to 20 weeks but remained stable afterward, suggesting that while linear synchrony decreases with age, some nonlinear interactions persist. These findings are illustrated in Figure 1B.

3.3. Psychometric Behavior with Logistic regression

Comparison of the three mice revealed age-related trends in decision-making. The youngest mouse, Cori (11 weeks), showed the lowest slope and lowest pseudo- R^2 , suggesting limited contrast sensitivity and less consistent use of sensory information. However, the intercept was near zero. These findings possibly reflect exploratory behavior or immature strategy use. Radnitz (20 weeks) demonstrated the highest sensitivity (steepest slope) and consistency (highest pseudo- R^2), though with a notable side bias, suggesting a mature and possibly habitual strategy. Moniz (30 weeks) showed intermediate slope and pseudo- R^2 values, with a moderate intercept suggesting a decline in sensitivity and consistency compared to Radnitz. These results support a behavioral peak in early adulthood, with reduced decision quality both before and after. Figures 1D and 1E illustrate these behavioral metrics and decision curves.

3.4. Contrast Sensitivity with Spearman's rank

The mice all achieved high accuracy at large contrast differences, but their behaviors revealed different strategies. Radnitz (20 weeks) showed strong, consistent sensory-driven performance with clear psychometric behavior and high contrast sensitivity, nearing 1.0 at high contrast. The highest Spearman correlation further confirms robust contrast sensitivity. Cori (11 weeks) displayed irregular accuracy, low contrast sensitivity, and low Spearman correlation, suggesting exploratory or inconsistent behavior. Moniz (30 weeks) showed improved accuracy; however, the minimal improvement in accuracy between 0.5 and 0.75 contrast suggests a performance plateau, indicating reduced sensitivity compared to younger adults. These results suggest a nonlinear age-performance relationship, with middle-aged mice showing peak decision-making,

younger mice exhibiting immature strategies, and older mice demonstrating stable but less flexible behavior (Figure 1F).

Figure 1. Age-Dependent Variations in Functional Connectivity and Decision Behavior

A. Mean Functional Connectivity Between MOs and Other Brain Regions Across Sessions.

B. Comparative Functional Connectivity Strengths Across Age Groups.

C. Average Accuracy and Response Time Across Age Groups.

D. Logistic Regression Metrics (Slope, Intercept, Pseudo-R²) for Individual Mice.

E. Psychometric Sigmoid Fits per Mouse in Session 2.

F. Accuracy per Contrast Level Across Age Groups.

4. Discussion

This study integrates neural recordings and behavioral analyses to uncover how aging impacts functional connectivity and strategic decision-making in mice. We found that MOs is tightly functionally coupled with prefrontal and basal ganglia regions during task performance but the functional connectivity tends to decline with age, particularly in networks associated with visual processing and sensorimotor integration. This observation aligns with prior literature on aging in both rodents and humans, which suggests that the aging brain exhibits reduced synchronization and diminished inter-regional communication. Second, we found that mice from different age groups used distinct behavioral strategies during a visual task where younger mice were more exploratory, while older mice adopted more conservative and consistent approaches. However, these strategic differences did not lead to consistent changes in accuracy or response time across age groups as shown in Figure 1C. This suggests that engagement or strategy type does not necessarily enhance performance, likely because task accuracy is strongly influenced by stimulus quality, such as image contrast. When stimuli are ambiguous or low in contrast, even an engaged animal may struggle to make the correct decision.

Future research should aim to distinguish behavioral lapses from true cognitive deficits by using real-time measures of arousal and engagement, such as pupil size, whisking, and movement. Building on current behavioral and connectivity results, the next step is to identify neural patterns that differentiate engaged from disengaged states—hypothesizing that engaged states show strong, stimulus-locked activity in MOs and primary visual area (V1/VISp), while disengaged states show weaker responses. Additionally, the dataset will be expanded to include more animals across a wider age range, enabling analysis of developmental and aging trends and testing the generalizability of observed neural and behavioral patterns.

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